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Multi-drug resistant TB is a biological weapon.

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Multi-drug resistant tuberculosis (TB) is a medical problem worldwide in developing and urban communities whose prevalence and criticality is influenced by endemic HIV-1 infection. We measured total transcription by microarray in the serum of humans with drug sensitive TB and in human with multi-drug resistant TB (MDR-TB). We discovered induction of a glycoprotein membrane protein encoded by *GINM1* in multi-drug resistant patients. We describe here activation of heat shock proteins in humans with MDR-TB. We present evidence for cell cycle regulatory activity induced by multi-drug resistant tuberculosis infection in the serum including induction of a CDKN family lincRNA.

GSE183787